

The user-researcher perspective

Initial findings for roundtable discussion

Top force: intention

The desire

Strong desire to carry out research that is equitable, inclusive and diverse.

Second force: the broader situation

Time pressure

- deadlines

Financial pressure

- lack of resource

Organisational flux

- staff change position / role
- staff / agency staff on short term contracts
- staff and project turnover
- changes in organisational structure, leadership, direction and role

Third force: doing research

Rigid and standardised procedure

- difficult and time consuming to adapt
- expectation to use templates / procedures which may not be accessible for everyone
- extra safeguarding procedures for 'vulnerable' participants
- expected to create usability tasks before recruiting participants

Tackling organisational culture

- ingrained ideas about diversity and inclusion
- helping clients understand good EDI practice

Working within organisational structure

- no authority to push ideas
- deadlines / delivery decided elsewhere
- usability testing is an afterthought / at the end of the project

Working within a defined project

- tight deadline
- budget
- scope decided by clients and stakeholders
- need to commit to approaches early – like ethical approval before recruitment

Getting guidance

- siloed teams – knowledge is spread not centralised
- lack of / unable to access guidance
- lack of feedback / dialogue between researchers and stakeholders
- creating usability tasks which are representative of diverse usage

Needing research credibility

- expectation of a single, predefined experiment with consistent procedures
- expectation of controlling for differences

Recruiting participants

- existing channels (databases) lacking diversity
- working with voluntary / faith groups but not able to develop long-term relationships
- project deadline pressures
- recruiting people who can fit available slots (see *research space*)

Getting access to research space

- lack of accessible, physical space
- limited availability of physical space
- needing the right equipment to support participants with usability tasks
- organisational restriction on communication technology options

Researcher worries

- ethical approaches, including compensation
- not knowing people's needs
- safeguarding participants and the research team

Fourth force: the reality

Working within restraints

It is difficult to take a flexible approach. Do the best I can within the constraints in which I am operating.